

one6G ASSOCIATION

Overview of one6G activities on THz communications

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March 30th 2023

[10.5281/zenodo.14188944](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14188944)

one6g.org

AN OPEN ACCELERATOR FOR 6G RESEARCH IN EUROPE

OVERVIEW

- Launched in **March 2021**.
- one6G is a **non-profit** and membership fee free association
- Offering an **open collaborative framework** to explore how to move beyond current communication networks technologies and business.

FOUNDING MEMBERS

VISION

one6G envisions a future where 6G technologies and solutions allow to unleash the potential of smart connectivity for a **secure, resilient and sustainable** development of our society and economy.

MEMBERS

As of Feb. 2023 (108 members from 28 countries)

Latest info please refer to: <https://one6g.org/members/>

ORGANIZATION STRUCTURE

one6G Board *(Chair, Secretary)*

WG1

Use Cases, KPIs, Future Market and Business Scenarios

Collecting and analyzing 6G related use cases, scenarios, and requirements

WG2

Enabling Technologies and System Architecture

Shaping the overall technology foundation

(THz frequencies, intelligent user plane / in-network computing, distributed / federated AI, next generation MIMO, integrated sensing and communication, NTN, etc.)

WG3

Communication and Dissemination

Community building and association promotion

(6G position paper, web portal, events, newsletter/news, liaisons, webinars, etc.)

WG4

Evaluation, Testbeds, and Pilots

From development to deployment

(Guidelines, gap analysis, testing procedures and certification, testbeds and trials, integrated sensing and communication)

General Assembly

WORKING PROGRAM

	Work Items	Scope of the WGs
WG1 Use cases, KPIs, and Future Market and Business Scenarios	WI 101 - Collection of 6G-related Use Cases and Related Scenarios (completed and in the maintenance mode) WI102 - 6G robotics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consolidate vision • Use case and requirements analysis • Streamline terminology, etc.
WG2 Enabling Technologies and System Architecture	WI 204 - Terahertz Frequencies WI 205 - 6G Radio Access WI 207 - Intelligent User Plane, In-Network Computing WI 208 - Distributed/Federated AI WI 209 - Next-generation MIMO WI 210 - Integrated Sensing and Communication WI 211 - Flexible Programmable Infrastructures WI 212 - Non-terrestrial Networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research of key enabling technologies, concepts, etc. • Evaluation and selection of most promising ones • Integration thereof into a coherent architecture
WG3 Communication & Dissemination	WI 301 - 6G position paper (completed) WI 302 - Dissemination: web page, social media, newsletter, one6G internal and external events, webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Liaisons and partnership management • Marketing and promotional activities • Preparation of workshops, conferences, etc.
WG4 Evaluation, Testbeds, and Pilots	WI 210 - (cross WG2/WG4) Integrated Sensing and Communication WI 402 – Definition of the evaluation guidelines for simulation/emulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aspects of testing and evaluation • Test procedures and verification • Testbeds, prove of concepts and trials, etc.

WI 204 – TERAHERTZ FREQUENCIES

- Started in November 2021
- Main objectives
 - Identification of potential use cases and application scenarios for THz systems
 - Study of channel measurement techniques and models for THz frequency bands
 - Investigation of main challenges and new approaches for the fabrication of THz devices
 - Analysis of global and regional regulations for THz bands
- Participants
 - Chair: Prof. Thomas Kürner (TUBS)

CHARACTERISTICS OF THZ BANDS

(one6G)

- ✓ Huge resource availability → extremely high data rates
 - 137 GHz of available spectrum in 275-450 GHz band
- ✓ Sensing and imaging capabilities
 - Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC)
- ✗ Harsh propagation conditions
 - Frequency- and distance-dependent propagation loss

USE CASES FOR THZ COMMUNICATIONS

- Three main use case categories

Fixed point-to-point applications

Application with mobile users

Integrated Sensing and Communication

THZ CHANNEL MODELING

- Harsh propagation conditions in THz bands have a strong impact on system performance
 - ↳ Channel characterization is of paramount importance for the design of efficient THz systems

THz channel measurements techniques

Time-domain spectroscopy

Vector network analysis

Broadband channel sounding

THz channel modeling approaches

Deterministic models

Stochastic models

Hybrid models

Main challenges

- Development of measurement systems able to operate at THz frequencies
- Characterization of new elements, such as ultra-massive MIMO antennas and RISs
- Derivation of new modeling approaches are needed for ISAC

Fabrication and deployment challenges

- High propagation loss → **difficult to satisfy link budget**
- **High directional antennas** are needed to compensate for **low transmission power**
- Small wavelength → **fabrication and assembly difficult due to small dimensions**
- **High fabrication costs** → not suitable for dense deployments

Future directions

Enhance electronics processes and low-cost fabrication

- CMOS, InP, GaAs, SiGe, and GaN
- Waveguide and assembly technology

Make use of new devices for long links

- e.g., replace solid-state power amplifiers with new-generation travelling wave tubes

one6G published the 1st position paper to lay out its vision and work plan in Nov 2021.

Vertical Use Cases and Requirements

Technology Pillars

- **THz frequencies**
- Radio Access
- Next generation MIMO
- Integrated sensing and communication
- Distributed and federated AI
- Flexible programmable infrastructures
- Non-terrestrial networks

6G technology overview – 2nd edition was published on Nov 10th , 2022

Contributors

- **THz Frequencies:** Thomas Kürner, Tobias Doeker (*TU Braunschweig*), Mate Boban, Tommaso Zugno (*Huawei*), Claudio Paoloni (*Lancaster University*).
- **6G Radio Access:** Israel Leyva Mayorga (*Aalborg University*), Nikolaos Pappas (*Linköping University*), Najeeb Hassan (*Huawei*), Peter Trifonov (*ITMO*).
- **Next generation MIMO:** Danaisy P. Prado Alvarez (*Universitat Politècnica de València*), Eduard A. Jorswieck (*TU Braunschweig*), Ferhad Askerbeyli, Mario Castañeda, Martin Schubert, Michail Palaiologos, Ronald Böhnke, Samer Bazzi, Tobias Laas (*Huawei*).
- **Integrated Sensing and Communication:** Andrea Giorgetti (*University of Bologna*), Richard Stirling-Gallacher (*Huawei*).
- **Distributed Federated AI:** Ramin Khalili (*Huawei*), Sokratis Barmounakis, Lina Magoula, Nikolas Koursioupas (*NKUA*), Claudia Campolo, Antonio Iera, Antonella Molinaro (*CNIT*), Elizabeth Palacios (*Universitat Politècnica de València*), George Karetsos (*University of Thessaly*).
- **Intelligent User Plane:** Susanna Schwarzmann (*Huawei*), Jari Mutikainen, Riccardo Guerzoni (*Docomo Euro-Labs*).
- **Flexible programmable Infrastructures:** Carlos Guimarães, Luca Cominardi (*ZettaScale Technology SARL*), Aitor Zabala Orive (*Telcaria*), Artur Hecker, Dirk Trossen, Zoran Despotovic (*Huawei*).

Download it here

<https://one6g.org/resources/publications/>

ONE6G OPEN LECTURE

one6G establishes open lectures series, as an open 6G knowledge sharing platform.

The collage displays several event pages for the ONE6G Open Lectures series. Each page includes the event title, date, time, and a detailed agenda. The events shown are:

- Lecture 1/5: 6G Network AI** (5 May 2022 - 14h00 CEST)
- Lecture 2/5: Integrated Sensing and Communication** (7 July 2022 - 14h00 CEST)
- Lecture 3/5: 6G testbed / simulation** (15 September 2022 - 14h00 CEST)
- Lecture 4/5: Flexible Programmable Infrastructures** (1 December 2022 - 14h00 CET)
- Lecture 5: Channel Modeling** (23 February 2023 - 13h30 CET)

Each agenda lists speakers and their titles, such as Slawomir Stanczak (Head of WITnet), David Gerber (Professor at Fraunhofer), and Monique Callati (CEO of Marvell). A QR code and the URL <https://one6g.org/events/open-lecture-5-channel-modeling/> are also visible.

Speakers include:

- **IEEE fellow:** Prof. Wolfgang Utschick
- **Multi-award winner:** Prof. Giuseppe Caire
- **National 6G platform leaders:** Slawomir Stanczak
- **Industry leaders from vertical sector:** Andreas Mueller from Bosch
- **Operator representative:** Telenor
- **one6G partners with active contribution to 6G testbed activities.**
- ...

CONTACT US TO LEARN MORE

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THANK YOU FOR YOUR ATTENTION

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